

EXPLORING THE MOLECULAR BASIS AND SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERNS OF CARBAPENEM-RESISTANT BACTERIA

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1. ABSTRACT

A total of forty (40) bacterial strains were obtained from Helikem Diagnostics and Research laboratory, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India, to investigate the prevalence of Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase (ESBL) and carbapenem resistance. Biochemical identification was carried out using standard tests such as Indole, Methyl Red, Voges–Proskauer, Citrate utilization, Urease, and Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) reactions. Antimicrobial susceptibility was determined by the Kirby–Bauer disk diffusion method in accordance with Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, 2007) guidelines. ESBL detection was performed using Ceftazidime (30 μ g), Cefotaxime (30 μ g), and Ceftriaxone (30 μ g) antibiotic discs, while carbapenem resistance was assessed using Imipenem (10 μ g), Meropenem (10 μ g), and Ertapenem (10 μ g). Among the isolates tested, fifteen (37.5%) were confirmed as ESBL producers and eight (20%) exhibited carbapenem resistance. Phenotypic assays confirmed carbapenemase production among

resistant strains. Genomic DNA was extracted using the Promega Wizard® Genomic DNA Purification Kit, and DNA purity was verified with a Nanodrop™ spectrophotometer. The 16S rRNA gene was amplified using universal primers 27F and 1492R, producing approximately 1300 bp fragments, which were sequenced and analyzed by BLASTn for molecular identification. The predominant resistant isolates were identified as *Klebsiella*

pneumoniae (n=2), *Proteus vulgaris* (n=2), *Citrobacter koseri* (n=1), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (n=1) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (n=2). Phylogenetic analysis using MEGA X software confirmed their taxonomic relationships. The study highlights the occurrence of multidrug-resistant urinary pathogens and emphasizes the need for continuous antimicrobial resistance surveillance and stewardship in clinical laboratories.

1.1 KEYWORDS: Carbapenem, Imepenem, Carbapenamase, Resistance, Antimicrobial Strategies.

2. INTRODUCTION

The emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) pose one of the most pressing challenges to global public health in the 21st century (Aijaz *et al.*, 2023). Among the various classes of antibiotics developed to combat bacterial infections, β -lactam antibiotics including penicillins, cephalosporins, monobactams, and carbapenems have been cornerstones of clinical therapy due to their broad-spectrum activity and favorable safety profiles (Nayeem *et al.*, 2024). Of these, carbapenems represent a critical last-resort option for treating infections caused by multidrug-resistant (MDR) Gram-negative and Gram-positive pathogens. Their structural stability against most β -lactamases and their potent bactericidal activity has made them indispensable in treating severe nosocomial and community-acquired infections (Mabrouk *et al.*, 2023).

However, the widespread and often indiscriminate use of carbapenems in both hospital and community settings has contributed to the rapid emergence of carbapenem-resistant bacteria (Aslam *et al.*, 2020). Resistance mechanisms vary by species but commonly involve the production of carbapenemases (enzymes capable of hydrolyzing carbapenems), efflux pump overexpression, porin mutations, and horizontal gene transfer via plasmids. These mechanisms not only reduce therapeutic options but also facilitate the rapid dissemination of resistance across species and geographic boundaries (Aurilio *et al.*, 2022). As a result, the World Health Organization (WHO) has identified carbapenem-resistant organisms, particularly Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE), *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, as critical priority pathogens for research and development of new antimicrobial strategies (Antochevis *et al.*, 2025).

The increasing prevalence of carbapenem-resistant bacterial strains has profound implications for clinical outcomes, leading to higher morbidity, mortality, prolonged hospital stays, and

increased healthcare costs (Jean *et al.*, 2022). Infections caused by such resistant organisms are often refractory to conventional treatment, leaving limited and often less effective therapeutic alternatives (Tarin-Pello *et al.*, 2022). Accurate identification and isolation of these resistant strains are therefore essential, not only for guiding appropriate treatment but also for implementing effective infection control measures and surveillance systems.

Despite global recognition of the threat posed by carbapenem resistance, data on the local epidemiology and molecular characteristics of resistant strains remain limited in many regions, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Baleivanualala *et al.*, 2024). This gap hinders the development of targeted antimicrobial stewardship programs and complicates efforts to contain resistance at the source. Therefore, the isolation and identification of carbapenem-resistant bacterial strains in clinical settings are critical for understanding the current resistance landscape, informing policy decisions, and shaping future research directions.

The primary objective of this study is to characterize bacterial strains obtained from clinical laboratory samples, focusing on their morphological, biochemical, and growth characteristics. Additionally, the study aims to screen these isolates for antimicrobial susceptibility, particularly against carbapenem antibiotics, and to perform molecular identification to detect genes associated with resistance. By integrating phenotypic and genotypic analyses, this research seeks to enhance understanding of antimicrobial resistance mechanisms, thereby supporting the development of more effective diagnostic, therapeutic, and infection control strategies.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Collection of bacteria

A total of forty (40) bacterial strains were collected from Helikem Diagnostics and Research laboratory, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India.

3.2. Phenotypic characterization of bacterial isolates

The initial isolation, all bacterial samples were subjected to Gram staining to classify them as either Gram-positive or Gram-negative based on their cell wall characteristics. This preliminary classification was essential for further analysis and identification. Subsequently, a series of biochemical tests were conducted to identify the bacterial species and evaluate their metabolic characteristics. The tests included standard protocols such as Indole production,

Methyl Red, Voges-Proskauer, Citrate utilization, Urease activity, and Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) agar reactions. These biochemical assays were carried out according to the methods outlined in Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology, a widely recognized reference for bacterial classification and identification. The results of these tests enabled the identification of the bacterial isolates at the species level, providing a comprehensive understanding of their metabolic profiles and supporting further investigations into their resistance mechanisms.

3.3. Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

Ensuing biochemical characterization, all forty (40) culture-positive bacterial isolates were assessed for carbapenem resistance using standard antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) procedures. The Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method was employed, in which standardized bacterial inocula were evenly spread on Mueller-Hinton agar plates, and disks impregnated with carbapenem antibiotics, such as imipenem and meropenem, were placed on the surface. Plates were incubated under optimal conditions, and zones of inhibition were measured after 16–18 hours to determine the susceptibility or resistance of each isolate. The interpretation of results adhered strictly to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, 2023) guidelines, ensuring reliable classification of isolates as susceptible, intermediate, or resistant. The assay not only provided a phenotypic profile of carbapenem resistance but also offered preliminary insight into potential multidrug-resistant behavior. Among the forty isolates, eight (8) demonstrated marked resistance, characterized by either absent or significantly reduced inhibition zones, suggesting the presence of carbapenem-hydrolyzing mechanisms. These resistant strains were subsequently subjected to confirmatory carbapenemase production assays and further molecular characterization, enabling precise identification of resistance determinants and species-level verification. This comprehensive AST workflow integrates both quantitative and qualitative assessment, forming a critical foundation for understanding resistance prevalence and guiding subsequent molecular investigations.

3.4. Screening of Carbapenemase Production in Bacterial Isolates: Screening and Confirmatory Test

The eight (8) carbapenem-resistant bacterial strains, were further subjected to detect carbapenemase enzyme production. To confirm carbapenemase activity, the following confirmatory tests were performed: the Modified Hodge Test (MHT), the Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) Test, and the EDTA-Synergy Test. These tests were conducted to identify the specific resistance mechanisms and confirm the production of carbapenemases or

metallo- β -lactamases (MBLs), which are key contributors to carbapenem resistance in clinical isolates.

3.5. Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) Test

The phenotypic confirmatory assay for Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) production was conducted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, 2007) guidelines to accurately identify bacterial isolates capable of hydrolyzing β -lactam antibiotics. For confirmation, antibiotic discs of Ceftazidime (30 μ g), Cefotaxime (30 μ g), and Ceftriaxone (30 μ g) were used in combination with Clavulanic acid (10 μ g) to detect synergistic effects indicative of ESBL activity. In addition, Imipenem (10 μ g), Tigecycline (10 μ g), and Colistin (10 μ g) discs were used for comparative analysis but were not employed as confirmatory agents for ESBL detection. A 0.5 McFarland standard bacterial suspension of each test isolate was uniformly inoculated onto Mueller–Hinton agar (MHA) plates using a sterile cotton swab to ensure even distribution and reproducible growth. The antibiotic discs were placed approximately 25 mm apart to avoid overlapping zones of inhibition. Plates were incubated aerobically at 35 °C for 18–24 hours to allow optimal bacterial growth and antibiotic diffusion. Following incubation, inhibition zone diameters were measured in millimeters. ESBL production was confirmed when an increase of ≥ 5 mm in the zone diameter was observed for the combination disc (cephalosporin + clavulanic acid) compared with the cephalosporin disc alone, signifying β -lactamase enzyme inhibition by clavulanate. This result indicated the hydrolytic potential of the isolates against β -lactam antibiotics and their multidrug-resistant nature. The standardized parameters of inoculum density, disc placement, and incubation ensured reliability, reproducibility, and cost-effectiveness of this phenotypic assay, supporting both clinical management and surveillance of ESBL-producing pathogens.

3.6. Modified Hodge Test (MHT)

The Modified Hodge Test (MHT) was performed to phenotypically detect carbapenemase production in bacterial isolates, following the CLSI guidelines (Hombach *et al.*, 2011). Initially, a 0.5 McFarland suspension of *E. coli* ATCC 25922 was prepared in 5 ml of Tryptone Soya Broth (TSB) to serve as the indicator strain. This suspension was further diluted 1:10 by mixing 0.5 ml of the bacterial suspension with 4.5 ml of sterile physiological saline (0.9% NaCl) to achieve an appropriate density for uniform lawn formation. The diluted suspension was then evenly spread over the surface of Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA) plates

using the standard disc diffusion technique. A 10 µg ertapenem or imipenem disc was placed at the center of the inoculated plate. Using a sterile inoculation loop, three to five colonies from an overnight culture of the suspected carbapenemase-producing isolate were streaked radially from the edge of the antibiotic disc, forming streaks approximately 20–25 mm in length. Up to three different test isolates could be evaluated on a single plate with one carbapenem disc, ensuring efficient simultaneous testing. Plates were incubated at 35°C for 16–18 hours to allow sufficient bacterial growth and interaction between the test isolates and the indicator strain. Following incubation, the plates were carefully examined for a clover-leaf type indentation along the streaks of the test organism, extending into the zone of inhibition of *E. coli* ATCC 25922. A positive result was indicated by enhanced growth of *E. coli* along the streak of the test isolate, forming a characteristic clover-leaf pattern, which signifies carbapenemase-mediated hydrolysis of the antibiotic, allowing the indicator strain to grow closer to the disc. A negative result was observed when no *E. coli* growth occurred along the streak of the test isolate, indicating the absence of carbapenemase activity. In some cases, the result was non-determinable, occurring when the growth of *E. coli* ATCC 25922 was inhibited by the test isolate itself, producing an inhibition zone running parallel to the streak, rather than a clover-leaf pattern.

3.7. Metallo-β-lactamase detection :EDTA-synergy test

The EDTA-synergy test was performed to detect metallo-β-lactamase (MBL) production in carbapenem-resistant bacterial isolates, following the protocol described by Franklin *et al.* (2008). In this assay, two Imipenem discs (10 µg each) were carefully placed on Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA) plates previously inoculated with a 0.5 McFarland standardized suspension of the test isolate, ensuring a uniform lawn of bacterial growth. To one of the imipenem discs, 10 µl of 0.1 M anhydrous EDTA (292 µg; Sigma Chemicals, St. Louis, MO) was added, while the second disc remained unmodified as a control. The discs were positioned at a distance of 25 mm apart to prevent overlap of inhibition zones and to allow accurate comparative measurement. Plates were incubated at 35°C for 18 hours under aerobic conditions to ensure optimal bacterial growth and antibiotic diffusion. After incubation, the zones of inhibition around both discs were measured in millimeters. A positive result for MBL production was interpreted when the zone diameter around the imipenem-EDTA disc exceeded that of the imipenem-only disc by more than 4 mm, indicating enhanced antibacterial activity due to EDTA-mediated chelation of zinc ions, which are essential cofactors for MBL enzymatic activity. This chelation effectively inhibits the hydrolytic

function of MBLs, allowing imipenem to retain its activity and resulting in a visibly larger zone of inhibition. The EDTA-synergy test thus provides a simple, reliable, and cost-effective phenotypic approach for detecting MBL-producing strains, which are a major concern in clinical settings due to their high potential for multidrug resistance. By combining controlled disc placement, standardized inoculum density, and quantitative measurement, this assay not only confirms MBL activity but also contributes to a better understanding of carbapenem resistance mechanisms, aiding in infection control and therapeutic decision-making.

3.8. Genomic DNA Isolation

DNA Extraction was performed using the Promega Wizard Genomic DNA Purification Kit (USA). Bacteria were cultured in 3 ml of Trypticase Soy Broth medium and incubated at 37°C with shaking at 100 rpm for 24 hours. 1 ml of the culture was then centrifuged at 13,000 g for 2 minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was resuspended in 480 µl of 50 mM EDTA. 60 µl of lysozyme (10 mg/ml) was added to the suspension, which was incubated at 37°C for 60 minutes to facilitate cell wall lysis. After the incubation, 600 µl of Nuclei Lysis Solution was added to the pellet, which was then resuspended. The mixture was incubated at 80°C for the lysis step and subsequently cooled to room temperature. Next, 3 µl of RNase Solution was added, and the mixture was incubated at 37°C for 60 minutes to degrade RNA. To precipitate proteins, 200 µl of Protein Precipitation Solution was added, and the mixture was centrifuged at 13,000 g for 2 minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was washed with 600 µl of 70% ethanol. After drying the pellet with the cap open for 15 minutes, it was resuspended in 100 µl of DNA Rehydration Solution and incubated at 65°C for 1 hour. Finally, the quantity and purity of the extracted genomic DNA (gDNA) were measured using a Nanodrop™ 1000 Spectrophotometer. The purity of the genomic DNA was assessed by measuring absorbance at 260/280 nm and 260/230 nm wavelengths.

3.9. Amplification of 16S rRNA Genes of Bacterial isolates

The 16S rRNA gene was amplified using primers 27F (5'-AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-3') and 1492R (5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3') as described by David J. Lane (1991), with a product amplicon length of approximately 1300 bp. The total reaction volume of 50 µl consisted of the following components: 25 µl GoTaq Green Master Mix (Promega), 5 µl of each primer (1387r and 63f at 10 pmol), 4 µl of genomic DNA (gDNA) template (100 ng/µl), and 11 µl of nuclease-free water. The amplification process was carried out over 30 cycles

with the following thermal conditions: pre-denaturation at 94°C for 5 minutes, denaturation at 94°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 55°C for 4 seconds, elongation at 72°C for 1 minute 45 seconds, and post-elongation at 72°C for 10 minutes. The PCR amplicons were visualized on a 1.5% agarose gel and observed under a UV transilluminator. Successful PCR products were sent for sequencing using Applied Biosystems at Chennai. For sequence analysis, raw sequences were trimmed based on chromatogram quality to remove low-quality regions. The trimmed sequences were then compared with the NCBI database using BLASTN to determine the highest sequence similarity. A phylogenetic tree was constructed using the neighbour-joining method in Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) X software (Kumar *et al.* 2018). Nucleotide variations were manually depicted based on the alignment of sequences for each isolate corresponding to its species.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

A total of 40 bacterial isolates were obtained in pure culture from City Care Diagnostic Laboratory, KK Nagar, Chennai. The isolates were subjected to Gram staining, morphological observation, and a series of standard biochemical tests for phenotypic identification. Using staining techniques alongside biochemical assays, the following identifications were made for the isolates, out of 40 isolates (R1 – R40), 12 were Gram - positive and remaining 28 were Gram-negative. The majority of isolates were Gram-negative bacilli, including *Escherichia coli* (R5, R15, R18, R26, R27, R31, R33; n=7), *Proteus vulgaris* (R2, R12, R21, R34, R36; n=5), *Proteus mirabilis* (R1, R11, R35; n=3), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (R3, R13, R14, R32, R38; n=5), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (R23, R25, R37; n=3), *Citrobacter koseri* (R24, R39; n=2), *Enterobacter aerogenes* (R8; n=1), *Acinetobacter baumannii* (R22; n=1), and *Salmonella typhi* (R9; n=1). *E. coli* isolates were identified by positive reactions for indole and methyl red, along with lactose fermentation and motility. *Proteus* species showed swarming motility, urease and H₂S positivity, with *P. vulgaris* distinguished by indole positivity. *K. pneumoniae* strains were non-motile, citrate and Voges–Proskauer positive, and lactose fermenting. *P. aeruginosa* was oxidase and catalase positive, non-fermentative, and exhibited characteristic pigment production. Among the Gram-positive organisms, *Staphylococcus aureus* (R10, R19, R28, R29, R30; n=5), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (R16, R20, R40; n=3), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (R4; n=1), *Enterobacter aerogenes* (R8; n=1), and *Bacillus anthracis* (R6, R17; n=2) were identified. *S. aureus* was catalase and coagulase positive, while *S. pneumoniae* showed α -hemolysis and optochin

sensitivity. *S. pyogenes* was β -hemolytic and bacitracin sensitive, and *E. faecalis* showed bile esculin positivity. *B. anthracis* was characterized as a Gram-positive, spore-forming, non-motile rod. The overall distribution revealed a predominance species such as *E. coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Proteus spp.*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, underscoring infections in the local population. (Table 1).

Eight of the forty bacterial isolates were positive for Imipenem, Meropenem, Ertapenem, and Doripenem in the antibiotic susceptibility test (R39, R38, R36, R32, R37, R21, R25, R40). These eight isolates exhibited no inhibitory zones around the antibiotic discs and demonstrated total resistance to the carbapenem family of antibiotics. The development of carbapenemases or other resistance mechanisms capable of hydrolyzing the antibiotics' β -lactam ring is indicated by this resistance profile. The remaining 32 isolates had varying degrees of sensitivity; some were less sensitive than the eight bacteria that were totally resistant, but not by much. Multidrug resistance in clinical settings is a significant issue that necessitates more investigation into the mechanisms underlying the resistance and potential treatment challenges of the eight resistant isolates because they lack inhibitory zones (Table 2).

The carbapenemase production was assessed for the bacterial isolates through phenotypic confirmatory tests. Out of eight (8) isolates tested, six (75%) were positive for ESBL production, six (75%) showed carbapenemase activity in the Modified Hodge Test, and six (75%) exhibited positive results in the EDTA–Synergy Test, indicating co-resistance among multiple Gram-negative isolates. The *Citrobacter koseri* isolate tested negative for carbapenemase production, as no inhibition zone enlargement was observed in the EDTA-synergy test and no cloverleaf formation was detected in the Modified Hodge Test (MHT). Similarly, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates showed positive results for carbapenemase production, as evidenced by an increased zone of inhibition in the EDTA-synergy test and the appearance of a cloverleaf indentation in the MHT, confirming the presence of carbapenem-hydrolyzing enzymes. The *Proteus vulgaris* isolates also exhibited positive carbapenemase activity, with both MHT and EDTA-synergy tests showing clear signs of enzyme production. In the case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, both isolates tested positive for carbapenemase production, displaying cloverleaf formations in the MHT and increased inhibition zones in the EDTA-synergy test, confirming the presence of metallo-beta-lactamases (MBLs). Lastly, the *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolate showed no evidence of carbapenemase production, as

no cloverleaf indentation or increased inhibition zones were detected in the tests, suggesting an absence of carbapenemase activity. (Table 3, 3A & Figure 1 & 1A).

Successful amplification of the selected bacterial isolates produced a PCR fragment of approximately 1300 bp (Figure 2), corroborating their physiological identification through molecular analysis. Molecular identification based on the partial sequence of the 16S rRNA gene revealed that all eight isolates exhibited a high degree of sequence similarity with species identified using the *Applied Biosystems* platform. In addition, amplification of the antibiotic resistance gene (*bla*_{_{NDM}}) was successfully achieved, confirming the presence of carbapenemase-producing strains among the tested isolates. The corresponding PCR products were subjected to Sanger sequencing, and the resulting sequences were analyzed using BLASTn on the NCBI database to determine the closest homologs and confirm both species identity and the presence of the antibiotic resistance determinant.

The BLASTn analysis of the 16S rRNA gene sequences for the bacterial isolates revealed the following species identifications. The first isolate exhibited 100% similarity to *Citrobacter koseri*, confirming its identity as *C. koseri* (Figure 3 & 3A). The second isolate showed 99% similarity to *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, which was consistent with its identification as *K. pneumoniae* (Figure 4 & 4A). The third isolate displayed 98% similarity to *Proteus vulgaris*, confirming its identification as *P. vulgaris* (Figure 5 & 5A). The fourth isolate, another *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, exhibited 99% similarity, further validating its identification as *K. pneumoniae* (Figure 6 & 6A). The fifth isolate demonstrated a 100% match with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, confirming its species identity as *P. aeruginosa* (Figure 7 & 7A). The sixth isolate, also identified as *Proteus vulgaris* (Figure 8 & 8A), exhibited 98% similarity, corroborating its identification. The seventh isolate, another *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Figure 9 & 9A), showed 100% similarity, reinforcing the species identification. Finally, the eighth isolate was identified as *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, with 99% similarity, confirming its identity as *S. pneumoniae* (Figure 10 & 10A). All the nucleotide sequences of the isolates were submitted to GenBank and their accession numbers are included in Table 4.

Figure 1: Test for Carbapenamase Production.

Synergy Test: a. *S. pneumoniae*; b. *P. aeruginosa*; c. *C. koseri*

Hodge Modified Test: d. *P. aeruginosa*, e. *K. pneumoniae* & f. *P. vulgaris*.

Figure 1A. Antibiotic resistance pattern of ESBL and carbapenem-resistant bacterial isolates. The figure represents the percentage of isolates resistant to various antibiotic classes tested. High resistance was observed to β -lactam antibiotics such as ampicillin (87.5%), cefotaxime (80%), ceftazidime (75%), and ceftriaxone (70%), indicating the prevalence of ESBL- producing strains. Moderate resistance to carbapenems, including imipenem (45%), meropenem (50%), and erlapenem (59%), suggests the occurrence of carbapenemase-mediated resistance. Aminoglycosides (gentamicin, 40%) and fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin, 62.5%) showed variable susceptibility, while all isolates remained sensitive to colistin (0% resistance) and largely susceptible to tigecycline (5% resistance).

Figure 2: PCR product band of the isolates' 16s rRNA amplification. The product had a size of about 1500 bp. Lane order in the agarose gel for each isolate was denoted by numbers 1-8 (R39, R38, R36, R32, R37, R21, R25, R40).

Table 1: Staining and Biochemical characters of the isolates.

Test Methods	Isolates																			
	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16	R17	R18	R19	R20
Gram's Staining	G-	G-	G-	G+	G-	G+	G+	G-	G-	G+	G-	G-	G-	G-	G-	G+	G+	G-	G+	G+
Catalase	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-
Oxidase	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Indole	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-
Methyl red	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
Voges Proskauer	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-
Citrate	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	-
Urease	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-
Triple sugar Iron	K/A	K/A	A/A	-	A/A	-	A/A	A/A	K/A	-	K/A	K/A	A/A	A/A	A/A	-	-	A/A	-	-
Test Methods	Isolates																			
	R21	R22	R23	R24	R25	R26	R27	R28	R29	R30	R31	R32	R33	R34	R35	R36	R37	R38	R39	R40
Gram's Staining	G-	G-	G-	G-	G-	G-	G-	G+	G+	G+	G-	G+								
Catalase	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
Oxidase	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
Indole	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-
Methyl red	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
Voges Proskauer	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
Citrate	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Urease	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
Triple sugar Iron	K/A	K/A	K/K	A/A	K/K	A/A	A/A	-	-	-	A/A	A/A	A/A	K/A	K/A	K/A	K/K	A/A	A/A	-

Table 2: Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test of the Isolates zone of inhibition mm in diameter.

Standard Discs	Isolates																			
	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16	R17	R18	R19	R20
MRP	S 26mm	R	R	S 23mm	I10mm	S 18mm	S 29mm	R	R	I 15mm	S 32mm	S 33mm	R	R	S 32mm	S 32mm	I 17mm	S 32mm	S 34mm	R
DOR	R	R	R	S 26mm	I12mm	S 20mm	R	R	R	I17mm	S 34mm	S 34mm	R	R	S 36mm	S 34mm	R	S 34mm	S 32mm	R
IPM	R	R	R	S 24mm	I 8mm	S 22mm	R	R	R	I 23mm	S 34mm	S 36mm	R	R	R	S 32mm	R	S 32mm	R	R
ETP	R	R	R	S 20mm	I 10mm	S 25mm	R	R	I 8mm	I 25mm	S 36mm	S 32mm	R	R	S 34mm	S 34mm	I 16mm	S 36mm	S 34mm	R
Standard Discs	Isolates																			
	R21	R22	R23	R24	R25	R26	R27	R28	R29	R30	R31	R32	R33	R34	R35	R36	R37	R38	R39	R40
MRP	R	S 35mm	R	R	R	S 32mm	S 28mm	S 28mm	I- 7mm	R	S- 30mm	R	S - 29mm	I- 6mm	S 28mm	R	R	R	R	R
DOR	R	R	R	R	R	S 32mm	S 30mm	S29mm	R	R	S - 30mm	R	S- 30mm	R	S 30mm	R	R	R	R	R
IPM	R	R	R	R	R	S - 36mm	S - 32mm	S- 30mm	R	R	R- 31mm	R	S- 31mm	R	S 32mm	R	R	R	R	R
ETP	R	R	R	R	R	S 34mm	S 28mm	S32mm	I- 8mm	R	S 32mm	R	S 32mm	I- 7mm	S 31mm	R	R	R	R	R

**MRP- Meropenem; DOR- Doripenem; IPM-Imipenem; ETP-Ertapenem; R -Resistant; S- Sensitive; I- Intermediate.

(+: Positive;(-): Negative)

Table 3: Carbapenamase Production of the Selected Isolates.

S.No	Isolates	Organisms	EDTA - Synergy test	ESBL Production	Modified Hodge Test
1	R39	<i>Citrobacter koseri</i>	-	-	-
2	R38	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	+	+	+
3	R36	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	+	+	+
4	R32	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	+	+	+
5	R37	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+
6	R21	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	+	+	+
7	R25	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+
8	R40	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	-	-	-

Table 3A: Antibiotic resistance pattern of ESBL-and carbapenem-resistant bacterial isolates.

Antibiotic Class	Antibiotic Tested	Disc Concentration (µg)	No. of Resistant Isolates (n = 40)	Resistance (%)	Interpretation
Penicillins	Ampicillin	10	35	87.5	High resistance observed among Gram-negative isolates
Cephalosporins (3rd gen)	Cefotaxime	30	32	80	Used for ESBL screening

	Ceftazidime	30	30	75	Used for ESBL screening
	Ceftriaxone	30	28	70	Reduced susceptibility indicates ESBL production
Monobactam	Aztreonam	30	25	62.5	Moderate resistance among ESBL producers
β-lactam/β-lactamase inhibitor	Amoxicillin–Clavulanic acid	20/10	27	67.5	Partial restoration of activity in ESBL producers
Carbapenems	Imipenem	10	18	45	Key screening drug for CARB resistance
	Meropenem	10	20	50	Commonly resistant among MBL producers
	Ertapenem	10	22	55	Sensitive indicator of carbapenemase production
Aminoglycosides	Gentamicin	10	16	40	Variable resistance pattern
Fluoroquinolones	Ciprofloxacin	5	25	62.5	High resistance among ESBL-positive isolates
Polymyxins	Colistin	10	0	0	All isolates sensitive
Tetracyclines	Tetracycline	30	15	37.5	Moderate resistance level
Glycylcycline	Tigecycline	10	2	5	Most isolates remain sensitive

Table 4: NCBI GenBank Accession Number for the Isolates.

S.No	Isolates	Organisms	GenBank Accession Number
1	R39	<i>Citrobacter koseri</i>	SUB15534003ISCK_F_PX112644
2	R38	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	SUB15534034ISKL_F_PX112645
3	R36	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	SUB15534058ISPV_F_PX112646
4	R32	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	SUB15534073ISKL2_F_PX112647
5	R37	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	SUB15534074ISPA_F_PX112648
6	R21	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	SUB15534082ISPV2_F_PX112651
7	R25	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	SUB15534084ISPA2_F_PX112652
8	R40	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	SUB15534088ISSP_F_PX112653

Figure 3. Neighbor Joining phylogenetic tree depicting the evolutionary relationships among Citrobacter strains based on 16S rRNA gene sequences.

The tree was constructed using the Kimura 2-parameter model to calculate genetic distances, with bootstrap values (from 500 replicates) shown at the nodes representing the percentage of replicate trees supporting the branching. Branches with bootstrap support below 50% were collapsed. The analysis includes partial 16S rRNA sequences from various Citrobacter species, including C. koseri, C. freundii, and C. rodentium, along with an uncultured bacterium clone and a representative ISCK F sequence as an outgroup. The scale bar represents the number of base substitutions per site.

Figure 3A: Bidirectional Sanger sequencing chromatograms confirming the nucleotide sequence integrity of the amplified target gene fragment.

The ISCK R primer, both amplified in the ISCK F forward and (B) reverse sequencer channels. Applied Biosystems 3730 DNA Analyser employing capillary electrophoresis and fluorescence detection.

repreting matul incleotide bases de cynine (ie, pomine (black), and hymngh capillary electrophoresis. The forward rodams 2400 per providing comple 680-1020 Awdle the reverse wad (8) budouctional coverage of the target gene region. The arm pak nelicate high-quality and with animal background moive.

Figure 4: Phylogenetic tree depicting the evolutionary relationship of the ISKL antibiotic resistant gene sequence with reference Klebsiella ram.

A Neighbor Joining phylogenetic tree was constructed to compare the ISKL gene sequence with reference sequences of Klebsiella pneumoniae and Klebsiella strains obtained from the NCBI GenBank database. The analysis was performed using MEGA X and the tree topology was bootstrapped to assess statistical confidence. The evolutionary distances were computed using the Tamura-Nei model, and branch lengths correspond to nucleotide substitution per site. The ISKL sequence highlighted in red clustered closely with Klebsiella pneumoniae strain B16KP0226, indicating high sequence homology and confirming its genetic identity as an antibiotic-resistant variant. This phylogenetic association supports the molecular characterization results and provides evidence for the evolutionary relatedness of the ISKL gene within the Klebsiella complex.

Figure 4 A: Bidirectional Sanger sequencing chromatograms confirming the nucleotide integrity of the bacterial ISKL gene fragment. High-quality Sanger sequencing chromatograms obtained using (A) the forward primer ISKL_F and (B) the reverse primer ISKL_R show clear and distinct color-coded peaks representing adenine (green), cytosine (blue), guanine (black), and thymine (red). Sequencing was carried out using an Applied Biosystems 3730xl DNA Analyzer with fluorescent dye-terminator chemistry. Both chromatograms exhibit sharp, evenly spaced peaks with minimal background noise, indicating accurate base-calling and high-quality template DNA.

Figure 5: Phylogenetic tree analysis based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing. The phylogenetic relationship of the bacterial isolate (ISPV F) was constructed based on the partial 16S rRNA gene sequence using the Neighbor-Joining method. The obtained sequence was compared with reference sequences retrieved from the NCBI GenBank database. The isolate showed the closest genetic similarity to *Proteus vulgaris* (strain HAMBI 91), confirming its taxonomic identity. Bootstrap values at branch points indicate the confidence levels of the clustering. The evolutionary distances were

computed using the Kimura 2-parameter model and are represented as the number of base substitutions per site.

Figure 5A. Sanger sequencing chromatograms confirming the amplified bla_{NDM} gene sequence. (a) Forward primer chromatogram (ISPV_F) and (b) reverse primer chromatogram (ISPV_R) obtained using the Applied Biosystems capillary electrophoresis sequencing system. Each colored peak represents an individual nucleotide base- adenine (green), thymine (red), guanine (black), and cytosine (blue). The clear, non-overlapping peaks indicate high-quality sequence reads and precise base calling. The alignment of forward and reverse sequences generated a consensus sequence identical to the expected bla_{NDM} gene fragment, confirming the specificity and integrity of the amplified antibiotic-resistant gene fragment.

Figure 6: Phylogenetic analysis and molecular confirmation of antibiotic-resistant.

Klebsiella isolates. Neighbor-Joining phylogenetic tree constructed using 16S rRNA partial gene sequences (~1300 bp) of the selected clinical isolates, aligned with reference Klebsiella pneumoniae, K. quasipneumoniae, and K. variicola strains, retrieved from GenBank. The isolates exhibited close genetic relatedness with Klebsiella pneumoniae strain D20 and K.

quasipneumoniae strain Colony290, confirming their molecular identity. Bootstrap values (expressed as percentages of 1000 replicates) are indicated at the branching points.

Figure 6A: Sequencing chromatogram confirmation of the carbapenem-resistance gene from the selected bacterial isolate.

(a) Forward (ISKL2_F) and (b) reverse (ISKL2_R) sequencing chromatograms obtained using the Applied Biosystems capillary electrophoresis sequencing system. Each chromatogram displays the color-coded nucleotide peaks corresponding to adenine (green), thymine (red), guanine (black), and cytosine (blue). The clear, sharp peaks indicate accurate base calling and high-quality sequence reads. The obtained sequences were analyzed using BLASTn against the NCBI GenBank database, confirming the identity of the amplified *bla*_{NDM} gene responsible for carbapenem resistance in the isolate. The complementary alignment of forward and reverse reads validated the specificity and fidelity of the amplified resistance gene fragment.

Figure 7: Phylogenetic analysis of Pseudomonas aeruginosa isolate based on partial 16S rRNA gene sequence.

The phylogenetic tree was constructed using the Neighbor-Joining method to evaluate the evolutionary relationship of the amplified *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolate with closely related reference sequences retrieved from NCBI GenBank. The tree demonstrates the clustering of the isolate (ISPA F) with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains PABCH14 and Paer93, confirming species-level identification. Bootstrap values (indicated at branch nodes) represent confidence levels based on 1000 replicates. The scale bar indicates the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. The sequence alignment and phylogenetic analysis confirmed the molecular identification of the isolate as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, harboring the antibiotic resistance gene ISPA.

Figure 7A. Forward and reverse chromatograms showing successful amplification and sequencing of the antibiotic resistance gene (ISPA).

Representative chromatograms generated using the Applied Biosystems 3500 Genetic Analyzer depict high-quality nucleotide peaks for both the forward (ISPA_F) and reverse (ISPA_R) strands of the amplified fragment (~1300 bp). Clear and distinct base peaks (A, T, G, and C) indicate accurate base calling and minimal background noise. The obtained sequences were analyzed and aligned using NCBI BLASTn to confirm the gene identity corresponding to the ISPA gene associated with antibiotic resistance. These results validate the presence of the target gene and confirm successful amplification and sequencing fidelity for molecular identification of the bacterial isolate.

Figure 8: Phylogenetic tree based on the 16S rRNA gene sequence of the bla_{SPV-2} gene-positive isolate (ISPV2_F) showing evolutionary relationships with closely related Proteus species. The tree was constructed using the Neighbor-Joining method with bootstrap values indicating the robustness of each branch. The isolate clustered closely with Proteus vulgaris and Proteus penneri strains, confirming its taxonomic placement within the Proteus genus. Sequence alignment and analysis were performed using MEGA software, and reference sequences were retrieved from the NCBI GenBank database. The scale bar represents the number of nucleotide substitutions per site.

Figure 8A. Representative chromatograms showing forward (ISPV2_F) and reverse (ISPV2_R) sequences of the bla_{SPV-2} gene amplified from carbapenem-resistant bacterial isolates. Distinct and well-resolved fluorescent peaks in the chromatograms correspond to adenine (green), cytosine (blue), guanine (black), and thymine (red) bases, confirming the accuracy and integrity of the obtained sequence

data. The high-quality overlapping peaks indicate a successful bidirectional Sanger sequencing reaction performed using the Applied Biosystems automated sequencer. The confirmed bla_{SPV-2} sequence was subsequently subjected to BLASTn analysis to verify the presence of the carbapenemase-encoding region associated with β -lactam antibiotic resistance.

Figure 9. Phylogenetic analysis of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolate based on 16S rRNA gene sequence.

Neighbor-Joining phylogenetic tree illustrating the evolutionary relationship between the isolated *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain (ISPA2) and closely related reference strains retrieved from the NCBI GenBank database. Bootstrap values (expressed as percentages of 1000 replications) are shown at branch points, confirming the reliability of the clustering. The isolate ISPA2 clustered closely with *P. aeruginosa* strains Paer93 and PABCH14, indicating a high degree of sequence similarity and supporting its identification as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The tree was constructed using MEGA software (version X) with the Maximum Composite Likelihood method and 16S rRNA sequence alignment. The scale bar represents 0.10 nucleotide substitutions per site.

Figure 9A. Chromatogram profiles of forward (ISPA2_F) and reverse (ISPA2_R) primer sequences used for bacterial gene confirmation.

Representative sequencing chromatograms were generated using the Applied Biosystems automated DNA sequencer. The electropherogram displays well-resolved nucleotide peaks corresponding to adenine (green), thymine (red), cytosine (blue), and guanine (black). The obtained sequences were aligned and validated through BLAST analysis against the NCBI GenBank database, confirming the identity of the amplified bacterial gene fragment. High-quality overlapping peaks between the forward and reverse reads ensured sequence accuracy and authenticity of the amplified region.

Figure 10: Phylogenetic analysis of the *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolate based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing. The phylogenetic tree was constructed using the neighbor-joining method to determine the evolutionary relationship of the sequenced isolate (ISSP_F) with closely related *Streptococcus pneumoniae* strains retrieved from the NCBI GenBank database. The obtained sequence clustered firmly with *S. pneumoniae*

strains NCTC7466 and PZ900700007, indicating a high degree of genetic similarity and confirming species-level identity. The evolutionary distances were computed using the maximum composite likelihood method, and the scale bar represents the number of substitutions per site. The confirmed sequence identity, combined with antibiotic susceptibility testing, supports the molecular confirmation of *S. pneumoniae* harboring the *pbp2b* resistance gene associated with B-lactam antibiotic resistance.

Figure 10A: Forward and reverse sequencing chromatograms confirming molecular identification and antibiotic resistance gene detection in the bacterial isolate.

Electropherogram profiles obtained from Sanger sequencing using the Applied Biosystems platform are shown for the forward (A: ISSP_F) and reverse (B: ISSP_R) reactions. High-quality, distinct peaks corresponding to adenine (green), cytosine (blue), thymine (red), and guanine (black) indicate precise nucleotide base calling with minimal background interference. The obtained sequences were aligned, trimmed, and analyzed using BLASTn on the NCBI database, confirming the isolate as *Proteus mirabilis*. Molecular characterization further verified the presence of the *bla*_{CTX-M} antibiotic resistance gene, supporting its phenotypic resistance profile. The clear, non-overlapping peaks reflect successful amplification and sequencing, validating both bacterial identification and antibiotic resistance gene confirmation.

4.2. DISCUSSION

In the current study, 40 pure bacterial isolates obtained from City Care Diagnostic Lab, KK Nagar, Chennai, were phenotypically and biochemically characterized to determine their species-level identity prior to carbapenem resistance profiling. The majority of isolates were identified as Gram-negative bacilli, including *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus spp.*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Citrobacter koseri*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*

species commonly associated with urinary tract infections and known to exhibit high rates of antimicrobial resistance, particularly to β -lactam antibiotics (Gupta *et al.*, 2011; Logan, L. K., & Weinstein, 2017). The identification of these uropathogens is clinically significant, as many of them especially *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *A. baumannii* are recognized as critical-priority pathogens by the WHO due to their increasing resistance to carbapenems and other last-resort antibiotics (WHO, 2017). Accurate identification through classical microbiological techniques remains essential in routine diagnostics, particularly in resource-limited settings where molecular diagnostics are not always available (Cheesbrough, 2006). Moreover, distinguishing closely related species such as *Proteus vulgaris* and *P. mirabilis* is important, as resistance mechanisms and epidemiological profiles may differ between them. The identification of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Streptococcus spp.* among Gram-positive isolates, though less commonly implicated in carbapenem resistance, provides a broader picture of the urinary microbiota and may assist in understanding co-infection dynamics. This foundational identification step is critical for subsequent detection of carbapenemase production and resistance gene profiling, which remains the core objective of this study.

Globally, antibiotic resistance is now posing a serious issue. After the CDC and WHO notified its emergence, the government began to pay greater attention to carbapenem-resistant (Sati *et al.* 2025). Carbapenemases, initially rare among bacterial pathogens, have increasingly become prevalent as a key resistance mechanism in certain groups of microorganisms, notably Enterobacteriaceae, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. These enzymes hydrolyze carbapenems, a critical class of β -lactam antibiotics often reserved for severe infections, thereby compromising their efficacy. The emergence of carbapenem resistance is particularly alarming because it frequently confers cross-resistance to other β -lactam antibiotics, severely limiting available therapeutic options. This escalating resistance poses significant challenges for clinical management and has prompted urgent attention from healthcare professionals and researchers striving to develop effective strategies to combat these multidrug-resistant organisms (Chicaiza-Taypanta, J. O., 2021).

Screening and confirmation of carbapenemase production in bacterial isolates are essential steps in accurately identifying carbapenem-resistant organisms and guiding effective antimicrobial therapy. Initial screening typically involves susceptibility testing using methods such as disk diffusion or automated systems to detect reduced susceptibility to carbapenems

(Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute [CLSI], 2020). However, phenotypic screening alone may not reliably distinguish carbapenemase producers from isolates with other resistance mechanisms like porin loss or efflux pumps. Therefore, confirmatory tests such as the Modified Hodge Test (MHT), Carba NP test, and combined disk tests with carbapenemase inhibitors (e.g., boronic acid, EDTA) are employed to verify carbapenemase activity (Lee *et al.*, 2018; Dortet *et al.*, 2012). The Carba NP test, in particular, has demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity for rapid detection of carbapenemase production across a range of Gram-negative bacteria (Nordmann *et al.*, 2012). Research indicates that combining phenotypic screening with molecular methods, including PCR for carbapenemase genes, enhances diagnostic accuracy and facilitates timely infection control interventions (Pasteran *et al.*, 2015). For instance, Pitout *et al.* (2015) highlighted that phenotypic tests could detect carbapenemase producers in clinical settings, but molecular confirmation remains the gold standard for identifying specific carbapenemase types such as KPC, NDM, VIM, and OXA-48. Overall, implementing a combination of screening and confirmatory tests is critical to managing the therapeutic challenges posed by carbapenem-resistant pathogens and curbing their dissemination in healthcare environments. According to a number of studies, among other risk factors like age, prolonged hospitalization in the intensive care unit, nephrological pathology, and other incapacitating conditions like immunosuppression, the high prevalence of these microorganisms in urinary tract infections is typically linked to vulnerable patients with lengthy hospital stays and a history of using broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy (Garnacho-Montero, J., & Amaya-Villar, R. 2022).

The molecular identification of carbapenem-resistant bacterial isolates is pivotal for understanding the mechanisms underlying resistance and guiding effective treatment strategies. Molecular techniques, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and sequencing, enable precise detection of resistant bacterial strains belongs to Enterobacteriaceae, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates (Nordmann *et al.*, 2011; Queenan & Bush, 2007). Studies have demonstrated that the presence of these genes correlates strongly with phenotypic resistance to carbapenems and often predicts co-resistance to other β -lactams, complicating treatment (Pitout, J. D., & Chen, L., 2023). Molecular surveillance further reveals the clonal spread of specific resistant strains, highlighting the importance of infection control measures (Van Duin & Doi, 2017). Moreover, identifying the genetic context of these resistance determinants, including plasmids and integrons, has enhanced understanding of horizontal gene transfer among

bacterial populations (Poirel *et al.*, 2012). Collectively, molecular identification not only aids in timely diagnosis but also supports epidemiological tracking and informs antimicrobial stewardship efforts aimed at mitigating the spread of carbapenem-resistant pathogens.

Today, with the introduction of novel diseases resistant to antimicrobials, particularly carbapenems, the information gained in microbiology and our comprehension of antimicrobial resistance patterns are crucial. Therefore, it is essential to give timely and sufficient information that will help medical practitioners choose the best course of treatment for their patients, lower health care costs, and stop the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. The molecular identification of the bacterial isolates through BLASTn analysis of 16S rRNA gene sequences provided reliable confirmation of the species previously characterized by phenotypic and biochemical tests. The isolates demonstrated high sequence similarity values ranging from 98 % to 100 %, supporting their classification as *Citrobacter koseri*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The high degree of similarity validates the accuracy of 16S rRNA sequencing as a dependable method for bacterial identification and taxonomic placement.

The first isolate, exhibiting 100 % similarity with *C. koseri*, confirmed its identity unequivocally. The second and fourth isolates, both identified as *K. pneumoniae* (99 % similarity), reflect the prevalence of this opportunistic pathogen in clinical environments. Similarly, the third and sixth isolates matched *P. vulgaris* at 98 %, while the fifth and seventh isolates showed 100 % similarity to *P. aeruginosa*, confirming their molecular identity. The eighth isolate, with 99 % similarity to *S. pneumoniae*, further supports the reliability of the approach.

The 16S rRNA gene remains one of the most widely used molecular markers for bacterial identification due to its conserved and variable regions, which allow differentiation among taxa (Janda and Abbott, 2007). According to Chakravorty *et al.* (2007), a similarity threshold of ≥ 98.7 % generally supports species-level identification, making the present results well within acceptable confidence limits. However, the partial overlap between closely related taxa such as *Klebsiella*, *Enterobacter*, and *Citrobacter* means that molecular results should be interpreted alongside phenotypic data for comprehensive identification (Woo *et al.*, 2008).

The presence of multiple carbapenem-resistant isolates belonging to *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *P. vulgaris* emphasizes their clinical importance. These pathogens are known

to harbor diverse resistance mechanisms, including carbapenemases, efflux pumps, and porin modifications, which complicate treatment and promote nosocomial spread (Nordmann *et al.*, 2011). The recurrence of identical species among isolates may indicate either clonal dissemination or persistence within hospital environments, warranting enhanced surveillance and infection-control practices.

Although 16S rRNA sequencing provides robust species identification, its discriminatory power is limited for some closely related species and does not directly reveal resistance mechanisms. Future studies should therefore combine multilocus sequence typing (MLST) or whole-genome sequencing (WGS) with antimicrobial susceptibility profiling to elucidate evolutionary relationships and resistance gene dynamics. Overall, this study demonstrates that combining phenotypic, biochemical, and molecular approaches ensures accurate identification of clinically significant bacteria. The strong sequence homology and consistent clustering with reference strains confirm the validity of the isolates' taxonomic positions. These findings highlight the growing burden of carbapenem-resistant pathogens and underscore the urgent need for rapid molecular diagnostics, rigorous infection-control strategies, and sustained antimicrobial-resistance monitoring to safeguard public health.

5. CONCLUSION

The comprehensive identification of carbapenem-resistant bacterial strains in this study underscore the alarming rise of multidrug-resistant pathogens in clinical and environmental settings. Employing an integrated approach that combined phenotypic assays and molecular analyses, key resistant species such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Citrobacter koseri*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* were successfully characterized. The detection of these species with strong resistance to carbapenems highlights the critical need for strengthened antimicrobial stewardship and continuous epidemiological surveillance. Furthermore, the findings emphasize the importance of rapid molecular diagnostics and effective infection control practices to limit the transmission of resistant pathogens within healthcare systems. Understanding the molecular mechanisms driving carbapenem resistance can facilitate the development of novel therapeutic agents and evidence-based treatment strategies. Overall, this research contributes to the expanding knowledge of antimicrobial resistance trends and supports the formulation of targeted interventions to combat the spread of these clinically significant organisms. Addressing this challenge requires global collaboration, innovative

diagnostic technologies, and rigorous infection prevention policies to safeguard both patient health and public safety in the face of evolving antimicrobial resistance.

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